

August 2019

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

**ANISOTROPIC THERMO-VISCOELASTIC RESIDUAL STRESS MODEL
FOR WARPAGE SIMULATION OF INJECTION MOLDED PARTS**

Zhiliang Fan, Paul Brincat, Alex Bakharev, Franco Costa, Russell Speight

Autodesk Australia Pty Ltd, 259 Colchester Rd, Kilsyth VIC 3137, Australia

- Introduction
- Viscoelastic Residual Stress Model
- Viscoelastic Data
- Validation & Calibration
- Numerical Examples
- Summary

Autodesk Manufacturing Solutions

Additive

Simulation

Generative

Subtractive

Robotics

Composites

Introduction: Injection Molding Processes

Gas-assited

Injection phase

Compression phase

Microcellular Injection Molding

Bi-injection

Co-injection

Overmolding on Continuous fiber-reinforced composites

Thermoplastics injection molding

Overmolding

Gas-assisted Injection Molding

Co-injection and Bi-injection molding processes

Compression molding processes

Reactive Molding analysis

Microchip Encapsulation analysis

Microcellular Injection Molding analysis

Powder injection molding

Resin Transfer Molding

Underfill Encapsulation analysis

Multiple barrel injection molding

Introduction: Simulation of Injection Molding

Warpage Cause: Shrinkage Variations

- Uneven cooling across thickness
- Non-uniform shrinkage across part
- Different shrinkage between part and insert

Warpage Cause: Anisotropic Effects

- Parallel and perpendicular shrinkages
- Fiber orientation, molecular orientation, Crystallinity
- Material property distribution

Shish-kebabs

Spherulites

■ True 3D Simulation

- Complex geometry (thickness transition, corners, chunk)
- 3D Material properties (composites)
- 3D flow and heat transfer effect at corners
- 3D fiber distribution at corners
- 3D stiffness representation at corners
- 3D shrinkage effect at corners
- Spring forward/spring back effect at corners
- Insert-overmolding
- Multi-shot-overmolding

- 10-layer Tetrahedral elements are used in this study.

- The residual stresses are affected by different process conditions such as melt temperature, mold temperature, injection velocity, packing pressure, packing time and cooling time.
- The stress relaxation occurs as the hot polymer is cooled down to room temperature due to viscoelastic behavior of polymer.
- A three-dimensional anisotropic thermo-viscoelastic residual stress model is essential for evaluating the effect of stress relaxation on molded-in residual stress, shrinkage and warpage of injection molded plastics parts.

3D Anisotropic Thermo-Viscoelastic Residual Stress Model

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = \int_0^t C_{ijrs}(\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)) \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{rs}}{\partial \tau} - \alpha_{rs} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} \right) d\tau$$

Where C_{ijrs} is the viscoelastic relaxation modulus, $\sigma_{ij}(t)$ is the stress tensor, ε_{ij} is the strain tensor, t is time, T is temperature, and $\xi(t)$ is a pseudo-time scale defined as $\xi(t) = \int_0^t \frac{1}{a_T} dt'$ where a_T is the time temperature shift factor that accounts for the effect of temperature on material response. α_{ij} is the tensor of thermal coefficients of expansion.

3D Anisotropic Thermo-Viscoelastic Residual Stress Model

➤ Viscoelastic Material Modelling: Generalized Maxwell Model

- $G(t) = G(0)\varphi(t) = G(0)[g_\infty + \sum_{k=1}^N g_k \exp(-\frac{t}{\tau_k})]$

where $G(t)$ is relaxation modulus at time t , which is evaluated at reference temperature. $G(0)$ is the instant modulus. N is the number of spring-dashpot Maxwell elements used, g_∞ is the long-term dimensionless modulus, τ_k represents the relaxation times, and g_k is the relative dimensionless modulus.

3D Anisotropic Thermo-Viscoelastic Residual Stress Model

- Incremental thermo-viscoelastic constitutive equation

$$\Delta\sigma_{ij}(t) = C_{ijkl}(t) \Delta\varepsilon_{kl} + q_{ij}$$

$$C_{ijkl}(t) = C_{ijkl}(0) \left[g_{\infty} + \sum_{m=1}^N g_m \frac{\tau_m}{\Delta\xi} (1 - \exp(-\frac{\Delta\xi}{\tau_m})) \right]$$

$$q_{ij} = \sum_{m=1}^N -\sigma_{ij}^{(m)}(t) (1 - \exp(-\frac{\Delta\xi}{\tau_m})) - C_{ijkl}(0) \left[g_{\infty} + \sum_{m=1}^N g_m \frac{\tau_m}{\Delta\xi} (1 - \exp(-\frac{\Delta\xi}{\tau_m})) \right] \alpha_{kl} \Delta T$$

Viscoelastic data for Material Modelling

Relaxation Spectrum

Master relaxation curve and Maxwell fitted curve with 10 modes.

g_i	λ_{dai}
0.08078	1.03E-06
0.093417	6.17E-05
0.139318	3.68E-03
0.455466	2.19E-01
0.226737	1.31E+01
0.00398	7.80E+02
0.000142	4.65E+04
0.000143	2.77E+06
1.61E-05	1.65E+08
4.99E-08	9.86E+09

Shift factor for Time-temperature Superposition

- WLF equation

$$\ln a_T = -\frac{C_1(T - T_r)}{C_2 + (T - T_r)}$$

- Arrhenius equations

$$\ln a_T = \frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_r} \right)$$

- Tabulated shift Data (original data)

➤ Both WLF and Arrhenius equations have a limited applicable temperature range.

➤ It is probably better to fit the shift data with two separate temperature range ($T < T_{ref}$: Arrhenius, $T > T_{ref}$: WLF)

➤ The best option is just to use the original tabulated shift data.

Validation & Calibration

Shrinkage data measured at Moldflow as part of material testing service

Measurements on 25+ moldings of tag die

- Differing conditions, thicknesses

Thermocouple

2mm in mold

Validation & Calibration: CRIMS

CRIMS (Corrected residual in-mold stress)

Experimental

Shrinkage Correction

Simulation

- molding machine
- mold geometry
- process settings
- material

- mesh
- boundary conditions
- solver parameters
- material data

measured shrinkage

predicted shrinkage
(uncorrected)

CRIMS Parameters

Regression Process

Validation & Calibration : CRIMS

MF Tagdie Models: Unfilled materials

Parallel Shrinkage of Polypropylene

* Some material data used in '3D uncorrected residual stress' are supplemental.

Validation & Calibration: Machine Learning

~3000 materials with measured shrinkage:
 ~2000 materials training
 ~1000 materials testing set

Predicting Shrinkage from:
 Viscosity, Thermal Conductivity, Specific Heat, $\rho v T$, Mechanical Properties, Thickness, Processing Condition

(By Courtesy of Nan Li)

Numerical Examples 1. Tagdie model

Material	Mat4745, PC+ABS, Unfilled
Mold Temp	55C
Melt Temp	250C
Injection Time	0.86s
Packing pressure	60MPA

The viscoelastic property is measured using a Rheometrics Dynamic Spectrometer in the Autodesk Moldflow laboratory.

- Relaxation spectrum at reference temperature
- Table-form time-temperature shift factor

Numerical Examples 1. Tagdie model

Packing time 20s

Model in the analysis	Predicted Shrinkage Cooling time 5S	Predicted Shrinkage Cooling time 20S
Viscoelastic model with shift table data	0.35	0.34
Viscous-elastic model	0.38	0.38

Comments:

- For viscous-elastic model, the cooling time has no impact on the predicted shrinkage value in this case.
- Due to stress relaxation, viscoelastic solution predicts less shrinkage than viscous-elastic model.
- Short cooling time lead to less stress relaxation than the long cooling time, and so the viscoelastic solution predicts larger shrinkage for shorter cooling time, but the difference is not significant.

Numerical Example 2: Rectangular Strip

Molded-in Residual Stress Validation

➤ Experiment data source:

- WF Zoetelief, LFA Douven and AJI Housz, *Polym Eng Sci* **36**(14): 1886-1896 (1996)

➤ Mold:

Fig. 4. Rectangular strip mold B (ABS) (dimensions are in mm).

Process Parameters.

ABS		
T_{inj}	K	513
T_{wall}	K	325/321
Q	m^3/s	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
p_{entry}	see fig.	13

➤ Material:

- Novodur P2X (unfilled ABS, CM12059)

Numerical Example 2: Rectangular Strip

τ_k	g_k
4.706e-9	6.058e-2
4.410e-6	1.037e-1
2.082e-3	3.467e-1
6.198e-1	4.884e-1
3.305e6	4.266e-4
2.746e8	1.415e-4

The dimensionless relaxation spectrum data with the long-term dimensionless modulus equal to zero.

Temperature (C)	Shift Factor
30	9.625e9
50	1.333e7
70	18465.0
80	687.207
90	25.576
99.85	1.000
105	0.0394
115	0.000342

Two shift equations of the material are replaced with an equivalent tabulated temperature-time shift relationship

Numerical Example 2: Rectangular Strip

Molded-in Residual Stress Validation:

- Residual stress measured by layer removal method

Fig. 16. Gapwise stress distribution specimen B (ABS).

Original graph from literature

- The 3D anisotropic thermo-viscoelastic residual stress model has been developed for tracing complex thermally-induced and pressure-induced stress build-up and relaxation.
- The viscoelastic master curve is fitted with a generalized Maxwell model and tabulated temperature-time shift factors are preferred.
- Stress relaxation reduced residual stresses slightly except in surface layers where the stress relaxation effect is larger. The effect of stress relaxation on shrinkage is modest in the numerical examples.
- The residual stress model calibration based on shrinkage measurement is an effective approach for improving the accuracy of shrinkage and warpage simulation.